

On mononitrosylcobalt(biguanidinium) complexes

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Manuscript received 20 November 2002, accepted 13 June 2003

A new six-coordinated mononitrosylcobalt(III)biguanide complex, $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2(\text{NO}^-)\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{2+}\text{SO}_4 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where, $\text{BigH}^+ = \text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7$), has been prepared by passing pure NO gas through the methanolic suspension of the freshly prepared bis(biguanidinium)cobalt(II) sulphate, $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, in nitrogen atmosphere. The structure of the complex and bonding of the ligand have been suggested from magnetic, electronic and IR spectral data. The NO is bonded to the metal atom as NO^- ion and the complex is feebly paramagnetic. The slight magnetic moment value of the complex is attributed to the T.I.P. contribution of mixing of ground level $^1A_{1g}$ term with higher energy level term. The sulphate is ionic and one water molecule is bonded to the metal atom, which completes coordination number six of the cobalt(III) atom.

A large number of nitrosyl complexes of cobalt and other transition metals are known^{1,2} but six coordinated nitrosyl complexes of cobalt(III) are few^{3,4}. Ghosh and Gupta⁵ have reported a diamagnetic violet complex, $\text{NO}^+[\text{Co}(\text{Big})_2(\text{NO})_2] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where $\text{Big} = \text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_6$). In this communication we report the preparation and characterization of a new mononitrosyl complex salt, $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2(\text{NO})\text{H}_2\text{O}]^{2+}\text{SO}_4 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (where $\text{BigH}^+ = \text{C}_2\text{N}_5\text{H}_7$).

Results and discussion

The complex is stable in dry air but decomposes slowly in the sunlight and moist air. On heating, the product gradually decomposes with loss of water and NO molecule. The complex is feebly paramagnetic ($\mu_{\text{eff}} 0.9 \text{ B.M.}$) at RT. The slight paramagnetism may be attributed to T.I.P. contribution as observed in some nitrosyl complexes⁶ or some slight impurities present. The reflectance spectrum of the complex displays three bands at 24300, 22200 and 18100 cm^{-1} . The bands at 24300 and 22200 cm^{-1} are attributed to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{1g}$ transition which splits due to lowering of symmetry in hetero complex, $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2(\text{NO}^-)(\text{H}_2\text{O})]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The second medium band is assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1T_{2g}$ transition in octahedral environment around Co^{III} atom.

The IR spectrum of the complex display a broad band at 3200–3500 cm^{-1} due to NH and H_2O stretches. The peaks at 990s, 1250m, 1390sh, 1620sh and 1980s, br cm^{-1} are similar to $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{OH}^-)_2]$ ⁹. A medium band at 620 cm^{-1} in the complex is attributed $\delta(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ of coordinated water. The new band at 1550 cm^{-1} in the complex

$[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)(\text{NO}^-)\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is attributed to $\nu(\text{NO}^-$ group¹⁰). The magnetic susceptibility result of the complex suggests oxidation state +3 of cobalt which is achieved by transference of an electron from cobalt(II) to nitrosyl group which makes it NO^- in the complex.

Experimental

Aquo-nitrosylbis(biguanidinium)cobalt(III) sulphate
 $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2(\text{NO}^-)\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$:

Freshly prepared silky yellow cobalt(II) bisbiguanide-complex¹¹, $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was suspended in ice cold methanol and pure NO gas was passed through it for 4–5 h when it completely changed to violet compound. It was filtered, washed with methanol and dried in air. The product is completely insoluble in organic solvents like methanol, ethanol, benzene, chloroform etc. (Found : Co, 13.96; SO_4 , 22.72; N, 35.66; C, 11.08; H, 4.98. $[\text{Co}(\text{BigH}^+)_2(\text{NO}^-)\text{H}_2\text{O}]\text{SO}_4 \cdot 1.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ requires for : Co, 13.66; SO_4 , 22.22; N, 35.65; C, 11.11; H, 4.39%).

In the reaction of NO in a similar manner with bis-(phenylbiguanidinium)cobalt(II) sulphate, no definite complex could be isolated, though some change in colour was observed. The dicyanobis(biguanidinium)cobalt(III) complex also failed to react with NO.

Acknowledgement

The award of a Teacher Fellowship by U.G.C. to one of the authors (B.R.) during the tenure of this work is thankfully acknowledged. Special thanks are also to Professor J. N. Chatterjea, for his time-to-time encouragement.

Note

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